

THE METHOD OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN ENGLISH CLASSES THAT MAKES USE OF ENGAGING EXERCISES, ROLE PLAYS, AND LANGUAGE SKILLS

Maxkamova Shakhlo Xasanovna

Teacher at Alisher Navo'i Tashkent State University of Uzbek language and Literature

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Abstract: This article discusses how to teach English to non-specialist students in the proper position and with interactive approaches.

Keywords: language skills, role plays, complex cognitive, physical and social interaction, activities.

МЕТОД ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА НА УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА, В КОТОРОМ ИСПОЛЬЗУЮТСЯ УВЛЕКАТЕЛЬНЫЕ УПРАЖНЕНИЯ, РОЛЕВЫЕ ИГРЫ И ЯЗЫКОВЫЕ НАВЫКИ.

Аннотация. В этой статье обсуждается, как преподавать английский язык студентам-неспециалистам в надлежащем месте и с использованием интерактивных подходов.

Ключевые слова: языковые навыки, ролевые игры, сложное когнитивное, физическое и социальное взаимодействие, виды деятельности.

INTRODUCTION

The interest that kids have in foreign languages these days is growing daily. Over the last twenty years, educators have been more and more focused on the practice of spoken language skills. Curriculum for foreign languages places a strong emphasis on communication competence and other productive abilities. One of the main objectives of language instruction, if not the most essential one, is for students to be able to carry in meaningful conversations in the language of instruction. Due to this change in focus, there is an increasing demand for educational resources that offer opportunities for supervised, interactive speaking practice outside of the classroom.

Almost every day, a student with strong analytical and quantitative intellect walks into our classroom, but their success in language acquisition is not assured. Furthermore, a large number of our most intelligent and quick language learners may even demonstrate comparatively low proficiency in analytical and quantitative reasoning. This work is made to help teachers of foreign languages understand intelligence in a new way. It wants to show them that intelligence is not just one thing, but can be different for each person. The goal is to help teachers learn how to teach in a way that helps all students in their class, no matter how they learn.

MAIN PART

Playing games and doing fun activities is really helpful when we are learning English. It doesn't matter if we are grown-ups or kids, playing games can make our lessons more exciting and make us want to learn more.

We can play games before our lesson starts, during the lesson to take a break from a difficult topic, or at the end of class when we have some extra time. There are lots of different games we can play with our classmates.

Guess the word.

- Divide the class into two groups, or more if there are many students.
- Choose one person from each team to sit in a special seat facing the class.

The board will be behind them.

➤ One person will write a word on the board. Then, another person from the team will try to help the person sitting in the special seat guess the word by using words to describe it. They have to do it quickly and they can't say, spell, or draw the word.

➤ Proceed until each group part has depicted a word to the understudy in the Hot Situate.

Health and illness

➤ Compose sicknesses or issues related to your most later lesson on post-it notes and adhere one post-it note on each students back.

➤ The understudies must blend and inquire for exhortation from other understudies to unravel their issue.

➤ Understudies ought to be able to figure their issue based on the exhortation they get from their peers.

➤ Utilize more complicated or darken issues to form the diversion more curiously for more seasoned understudies. For lower levels and more youthful understudies, report a category or reference a recent lesson, like "Wellbeing", to assist them along.

Make up sentences

This game requires some planning before the lesson.

➤ Type in out a number of sentences, utilizing diverse colors for each sentence. I propose having 3-5 sentences for each group.

➤ Cut up the sentences so you've got a modest bunch of words.

➤ Put each sentence into hats, cups or any objects you'll be able discover, keeping each isolated.

➤ Split your course into groups of 2, 3, or 4. You'll be able have as numerous groups as you want but keep in mind to have sufficient sentences to go around.

➤ Groups must presently put their sentences within the adjust arrange.

➤ The winning group is the primary group to have all sentences accurately requested.

There's moreover a few kind of way of learning English language. But it'll be more compelling once you utilize all dialect abilities: perusing, composing, tuning in and talking.

Listen. Listening is not just about hearing but also about understanding what is being said. In general, there are two types of listening: active in person or on the phone, etc.; and passive when we watch television or listen to the radio.

In this skill area there are also sub-skills that need to be learned. They include learning to "hear" the boundaries between words; learn to understand changes in intonation or stress, etc. What does it mean.

Speaking. Like listening, speaking can be active or passive. Active speaking is when we talk on the phone or face to face and there is interaction between the speaker and the listener. Passive speaking is when we speak without being interrupted or given feedback by others, for example: giving a speech or a teacher talking etc. Sub-skills here include pronunciation as well as use stress and intonation correctly. There are also more semantic skills such as how to choose the right words, how to build arguments, etc.

Reading. Reading is well developed in most societies. Secondary skills here include decoding script (for example, the Roman alphabet or Cyrillic or Chinese characters), recognizing

vocabulary, and selecting keywords in text. Here knowledge of syntax comes into play as does the ability to translate what is written into practical knowledge.

There are also important secondary reading skills such as reading skim, read to get the main idea. < br >, read for more details, etc. All this must be taught to students.

Writing. Secondary skills here include spelling and punctuation, using vocabulary correctly and of course writing in the correct style, whether formal, poetic or whatever the occasion, from shopping lists to vows at the wedding.

Today, too, there is not only the possibility of using a pen and to write, but also the possibility of using a keyboard or numeric keypad.

So language skills have been explained to you. The following tips will help you improve your language skills:

Reading is important for all of us. It strengthens our knowledge, it gives us an escape and it exercises our brain. The more you read, the more your reading and pronunciation skills will improve. Read topics that interest you, whether it's romance novels, sports magazines, newspapers, or car engine manuals.

Try writing a novel, short story, poem, play or any other creative genre. If you do it little by little every day, it will hone your writing skills and exercise your creativity.

As you listen, pay attention to good notes and important details the person says. Block distractions from your mind. Listen to other people speaking the same language to improve your speaking, writing and pronunciation.

Choose a topic and explain it. And make sure you speak loud enough for everyone to hear and speak with small words and big words mixed together. Discuss topic in your speech with others. Communicate a lot. Choose details from the reading in Part 1 and write them in Part 2. Explain the details out loud. Refer to the text to support your inferences, views, and opinions.

Explore language features and their effects. When speaking, use figurative language to make your point clear, for example: similes, personification, metaphors, etc. Use short sentences to clarify points. **Identify and explain the author's purpose.** Discuss it with others if possible.

- Analyze the author's diverse vocabulary. How does the author convey the message, mood, attitude, and emotions?

CONCLUSION

Experienced language teachers know that each individual learner has unique personality traits that determine their talents, abilities and interests in language learning: some are “fast” learners, some are thoughtful, some like to work independently, others need explanations and advice. And constant attention from teachers. This is why we must use the most effective teaching methods and materials available. Role-playing games, language skills, projects, video situations, games, activities can significantly expand our creative horizons in the proposed methods. Today, the entire English Teaching community is entering a new phase of interactive learning thanks to new technologies.

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